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COVID-19 and Climate Change: Determinants of Air Pollution in Six Metro Cities of India

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Abstract

This paper suggests a new approach towards measuring, modelling and analysing air pollution in the context of COVID-19 growth and control, climatic variables, and un-lockdown. The study is based on daily data from 25 March 2020 to 19 October 2020 on COVID-19 cases and air pollution in six metro cities in India. The paper constructs city-wise Air Pollution Indices (APIs) based on PM2.5, SO₂, CO and NO₂ constituents. It models the impact of the growth of COVID-19, lockdown/un-lockdown and three climatic factors determining air pollution, namely, temperature, wind speed and humidity. There are wide differences among the six metro cities, with Delhi being the poorest in terms of air pollution by considering four individual air pollutants. Another finding is that COVID-19 peaked on 18 September 2020, during the first wave. With the help of Generalised Method of Moments (GMM), the paper models and measures the impact of disease growth, disease control and climatic factors on city-wise API. In general, new cases reduced pollution. An unexpected finding is that recovery reduced pollution in 4 of 6 cities. This may be because those who recovered became more conscious or there was a lagged effect. Also, lockdown reduces and un-lockdown increases air pollution. Wind speed and humidity reduce air pollution and extreme temperatures increase air pollution.

Keywords: Air Pollution Index, COVID-19 peak, Metro cities, Lockdown and un-lockdown, Climatic factors

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Introduction

By now, the background literature on COVID-19 is very familiar and does not need an introduction or recap. In recent years, climate change has been aggressively championed by policymakers and scientists, and rightly so. But the new worldwide phenomenon of COVID-19 has raised numerous new challenges for both policymakers and scientists. The interest in this area of study has grown rapidly.

This paper focuses on the two-way relationship between the spread of COVID-19 and climate change. There are two trends in the literature surrounding the relationship between COVID-19 and climate change. The first trend investigates the effect of air pollution on the spread of the disease, while the second investigates the reverse, which is the effect of COVID-19 on climate change. Climate change variables are a mixed lot. The most obvious form of climate change that is easily observable is the effect of greenhouse gases (GHGs) on global warming. However, a less investigated angle is whether climatic variables like wind speed, temperature and precipitation affect air pollution—and if so, positively or negatively. In the present context, another dimension that complicates this relationship is how the growth or decline of COVID-19 affects climate change. And, yet, another important aspect is the indirect effect of COVID-19, which appears in the form of lockdown or un-lockdown, on the state of the environment in general and air pollution in particular.

The focus of this paper is on air pollution in India. However, for a better understanding of the subject, we have divided our work into two parts. The first studies patterns of air pollution and growth of COVID-19 in the country. The second models the determinants of air pollution with the help of a GMM model. We have combined three trends in the literature on air pollution, COVID-19 and climatic factors. Accordingly, our objectives are:

1. To measure the impact of the new cases and recovery of COVID-19 on air pollution
2. To measure the impact of climatic variables on air pollution during COVID-19
3. To measure the impact of lockdown /un-lockdown on air pollution during COVID-19

It is well known that climate change phenomena are related to:

1. Ionospheric changes
2. Anthropogenic changes
3. Extreme weather changes

While it is known that GHGs cause global warming and, in the long run, cause climate change and air pollution that affects health, it is a misnomer to attribute the spread of COVID-19 to pollution. COVID-19 is not an airborne disease and has no relationship to pollutants. Ramanathan and Feng (2009), however, point out the complex relationship between air pollution and global warming: “About 30 years ago, it was recognised that the increase in tropospheric ozone from air pollution (NO_x, CO and others) is an important greenhouse forcing term” (p. 37).

Also,

Until about ten years ago, air pollution was thought to be just an urban or a local problem. But new data have revealed that air pollution is transported across continents ... [and] increase atmospheric heating and tend to amplify greenhouse warming of the atmosphere. (p. 37)

From a social science perspective, it would suffice to combine anthropogenic and extreme weather conditions phenomena with the new global phenomenon of COVID-19 to comment on air pollution in this complex situation. Here, we take the example of urban India as a case in point.

The five pertinent research questions are as follows:

1. Do pollution patterns differ among metro cities?
2. When did COVID-19 peak during the first phase in India?
3. Does the growth of COVID-19 impact air pollution in India?
4. Does lockdown/un-lockdown impact air pollution in India?
5. Do climatic variables impact air pollution in India?

This paper has implemented the Jha and Murthy (2006) methodology to create and analyse a composite Air Pollution Index (API) for six metro cities in India. It has developed and estimated a Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) model for analysing this complex phenomenon that captures the three dimensions of the relationship between air pollution and the growth of COVID-19.

Literature Review

A sizeable amount of recent literature looks into the impact of pollution on the spread of COVID-19. In this context, Zhu et al. (2020, p.1) investigate the effect of air pollution on the disease. They state:

This study aimed to explore the relationship between ambient air pollutants and the infection caused by the novel coronavirus. Daily confirmed cases, air pollution concentration and meteorological variables

in 120 cities were obtained from 23 January 2020 to 29 February 2020 in China. We applied a generalized additive model to investigate the associations of six air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, CO, NO₂ and O₃) with COVID-19 confirmed cases. We observed significantly positive associations of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and O₃ in the last two weeks with newly COVID-19 confirmed cases.

Bontempi (2020) also purports that COVID-19 is aggravated (if not caused) by air particulate matter (PM):

The severe cases of COVID-19 infections in Italy, and notably in Lombardy (mainly in Brescia and Bergamo areas), registered at the beginning of March 2020, occurred after a period of PM₁₀ pollution, that exceeded the concentration of 50 µg/m³ (the attention limit) for several days. The two events were supposed to be correlated, also based on the limited information available about the new virus.

The second trend in literature is put forward by Otmani et al. (2020) whose study of the impact of lockdown in Morocco concludes:

A set of rapid and strict countermeasures have taken, including locking down cities, limiting population's mobility and prohibiting almost all avoidable activities. In the present study, we attempted to evaluate the changes in levels of some air pollutants (mainly PM₁₀, NO₂ and SO₂) in Salé city (north-western Morocco) during the lockdown measures.

A continuous measurement of PM₁₀, SO₂ and NO₂ was carried before and during the COVID-19 lockdown period. The obtained results showed that the difference between the concentrations recorded before and during the lockdown period were respectively 75%, 49% and 96% for PM₁₀, SO₂ and NO₂. PM₁₀ levels were much less reduced than NO₂.

Bashir et al., 2020 have similarly studied the relationship between pollution and COVID-19 in California, and they conclude:

We have evaluated the correlation between environmental pollution determinants and the COVID-19 outbreak in California by using the secondary published data from the Centers for Disease Control and the Environmental Pollution Agency (EPA). Our findings indicate that environmental pollutants such as PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂ and CO have a significant correlation with the COVID-19 epidemic in California.

In this case, the direction of the relationship is not clear because correlation is not causation.

Some of the extant literature points to the possible relationship between climatic variables and the disease (Holtmann et al., 2020). For instance, low

ambient temperature is said to be associated with the rapid spread of COVID-19.

Riccò et al. (2020) have questioned the central issue in their paper, “SARS-CoV-2 infection and air pollutants: Correlation or causation?”

Feng et al. (2019) attempted to examine the nexus between air pollution and climatic variables of precipitation and temperature to identify the nature of the correlation between global air pollution, represented by PM 2.5 concentrations, with global precipitation and global air temperature, respectively. As far as temperature is concerned, positive correlations were reported for a majority of the regions. Overall, the role of regional climatic variables appeared to be paramount in influencing the pattern of global air pollution. Meanwhile, a negative correlation was reported between air pollution and precipitation. On the whole, the study rendered useful insights on the climate–pollution paradigm, particularly on how to mitigate air pollution in the changing global climatic scenario.

Singh et al. (2020) have attempted to estimate the daily and temporal variations in air pollution using six air pollutants, namely PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, O₃, CO and SO₂, across different regions of India during the COVID-19 induced lockdown from 25 March to 3 May 2020. Variations in meteorological phenomena such as rainfall, wind speed and dust storms influenced the levels of PM_{2.5} in the atmosphere in many regions. These variations in pollutants during lockdown appeared to be the collective outcome of changes in meteorological conditions and the interplay of atmospheric elements, thereby warranting further investigation.

Approach Taken for the Study

The relationship between air pollution and COVID-19 disease is ambiguous in the extant literature. This relationship is confounded by the role of climate variables. Different researchers have shown different viewpoints, but there have been few econometric models that estimated and established the causality in this vital topic. Feng et al. (2019) and Singh et al. (2020) point out variations in this relationship at the regional level, “warranting further investigation”.

Our study is motivated by the need for and possibilities of investigating the relationship between air pollution and COVID-19 and climatic variables. Thus, the following three aspects have been investigated and measured.

1. Spread of COVID-19, recovery from the disease and its impact on air pollution
2. Effect of climatic variables of temperature, wind speed and humidity, on air pollution

3. Impact of lockdown and un-lockdown on air pollution

As stated previously, our main concern is air pollution, which is central to climate change. However, it needs to be noted that climate change is a long-term phenomenon and cannot be captured in the short-run (Murthy and Kumar, 2020). A window of thirty years is necessary to empirically test for phases in climate change. By definition, “Climate is defined as ‘average weather’, in terms of variability of temperature and precipitation over 30 years” (Murthy and Kumar, 2020, p.156).

Based on this definition of climate, we have chosen three climate variables:

1. Maximum wind speed
2. Average temperature
3. Humidity

We must point out that though precipitation would have been the ideal third variable, the lack of consistent data led us to choose humidity instead.

The six metro cities of India—Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, Bengaluru and Hyderabad—were chosen as the sampling frame of the study as they constitute the major part of the pollution in the country. It is possible to generalise the pollution levels in urban India based on these six cities. The air pollution variables (pollutants) considered for this study are:

1. Carbon Monoxide (CO)
2. Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5})
3. Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂)
4. Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂)

Data and Methodology

This section lays out the details of data sources and limitations. It also specifies the methodology, modelling and tests conducted.

Data Sources and Considerations

For this study, data was collected for the four major air pollutants (CO, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and SO₂) and the three meteorological variables (temperature, humidity and wind speed). Humidity was taken as a proxy for precipitation because data was not available for all periods. Both pollution and climatic variables were sourced from the Air Quality Open Data Platform operational under the World Air Quality Index (WAQI) project, a non-profit project started in 2007 in Beijing, China. The project provides transparent air quality information for more than 130 countries, covering more than 30,000 stations in 2,000 major cities and is published via two websites: aqicn.org and waqi.info.

City-wise data for India was collected for Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, Hyderabad and Bengaluru for the period 25 March to 19 October 2020 by accessing a new dedicated dataset of the WAQI project. The information, available at <https://aqicn.org/data-platform/covid19/>, is updated 3 times a day and covers about 380 major cities in the world. It has been functional since January 2020. The data for each city is based on the average (median) of several stations. The data set provides minimum, maximum, median and standard deviation for each of the air pollutant species as well as meteorological data. All air pollutants are converted to the US EPA standard (i.e., no raw concentrations). All dates are UTC-based.

For this study, we have considered median values for air pollutants and maximum values for meteorological variables. Consistent data for CO₂ was unavailable for the six metros; hence, it had to be dropped. COVID-19 data for daily new cases and daily recoveries was taken from the website <https://www.covid19india.org> for the same period—25 March to 19 October 2020. This study, however, has one limitation. Since city-wise data was not available for new cases and recoveries, this study has used all-India data for these two variables. The first phase of COVID-19 was from 25 March 2020 (national lockdown) to 19 October 2020⁸, which constitutes 209 data points. With the help of this data, we undertook the all-India estimation for determining the turning point in COVID-19, namely, the growth phase and the switch (the precise date) to the decline phase.

A Digression

In the context of data, certain statistical phenomena need to be understood. When any quantity (total active cases) starts from a very low level—in the range of hundreds—and in a few weeks, it increases to over a lakh, the initial growth rate is very high (as seen during lockdown). Ironically, when, at the time of un-lockdown (2 June 2020), numbers had reached a very high level and consequently the growth rate fell. Therefore, at low absolute levels, growth rates tend to be high and at high absolute levels growth rates tend to be low.

If β is the growth rate of new cases and α is the rate of recoveries, the net growth (δ), in active cases, remains positive until the rate of recoveries outstrips that of the new cases. This happens in a closed locality because as more patients get affected, fewer and fewer remain unaffected. The virus cannot find enough hosts who are not already immune post-recovery. This is the main cause of the turning point occurring in the trajectory of COVID-19. An exercise follows from the above analytical framework for determining the turning point in the COVID-19 trajectory.

8 This was the latest data available at the time of the study.

COVID-19 Growth and Decline

The growth of COVID-19 is a complex process. To study this growth pattern, a scientific method has been developed. In this section, a basic understanding of the dynamics of the process of COVID-19 growth at the all-India level has been laid out.

Three growth variables are involved:

g = Active cases of Covid 19;

b = Daily new cases; and

a = Daily recoveries.

The growth of COVID-19 can be captured by the net growth of active cases with the help of the following equation that represents the relationship between the three variables g , b and a and their growth rates, respectively: γ , β and α .

$$\gamma = \beta - \alpha \quad (1)$$

Where,

γ = Instantaneous Covid 19 growth rate

β = Growth rate of daily new cases

α = Growth rate of daily recoveries

δ = Daily compound growth rate

Growth equations:

$$\ln(\gamma) = \ln(b/a) \quad (2)$$

$$\ln(\gamma) = \ln(b) - \ln(a) \quad (3)$$

$$\ln(\gamma) = \log \text{ of instantaneous growth factor} \quad (4)$$

$$\exp(\ln(\gamma)) - 1 = \text{Daily compound growth rate } (\delta) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Turning Point} \rightarrow \ln(a) > \ln(b) \quad (6)$$

If $\beta > \alpha$ then $\delta > 0$; and $\delta > 0$ represents rising phase. If $\beta < \alpha$ then $\delta < 0$; and $\delta < 0$ represents declining phase. It is on this basis that the turning point, at the all-India level was established with the help of the predicted growth patterns.

We find that 18 September 2020 is the point of inflection at which the rising phase gave way to the falling phase. Figure 1 is based on the actual growth of daily new cases and daily recoveries. Figure 2 is based on the predicted values that incorporate the impact of lockdown and unlock down through an unlockdown dummy.

Figure 1: New Cases and Recoveries

Source: Author's compilation

Figure 2: Rise and Decline of COVID-19

Source: Author's estimate

City-wise Pollution

Almost invariably, Delhi has the highest pollution levels for all four air pollutants. The coefficient of variation (CV) is also almost always the highest for Delhi. Among the four pollutants, PM2.5 stands out as the main culprit, which is almost twice the level of other metros. The skewness is a result of Delhi's PM2.5 levels (Table 1).

In the subsequent analysis, it is established that the pattern of air pollution differs among metro cities not only in terms of its levels but also in terms of the weights of different pollutants. Each metro has a different composition of the four air pollutants. This is one reason why the generic official Air Quality Index (AQI) is not very representative and may at times be misleading. This is one of the motivations for creating a city-wise Air Pollution Index (API) and not relying on the standard AQI.

Table I: City-wise: Descriptive Statistics

Pollutant/City	SO ₂			NO ₂			CO			PM2.5		
	Mean	Std Dev.	CV	Mean	Std Dev.	CV	Mean	Std Dev.	CV	Mean	Std Dev.	CV
Delhi	5.0	0.1	2.0	9.2	0.2	2.7	7.2	0.1	1.6	111.9	2.6	2.3
Mumbai	4.3	0.1	2.2	3.9	0.1	2.3	3.3	0.1	2.5	57.4	1.8	3.2
Chennai	2.2	0.0	2.1	3.3	0.1	2.9	6.4	0.1	1.9	64.5	1.3	2.0
Bengaluru	3.7	0.0	0.9	5.5	0.1	1.1	5.6	0.1	0.9	66.3	0.9	1.3
Hyderabad	2.4	0.0	1.8	8.0	0.1	1.9	3.0	0.1	1.8	70.0	1.6	2.3
Kolkata	3.4	0.1	1.6	4.7	0.1	2.0	3.3	0.1	1.6	60.7	1.6	2.7

Note: US EPA units | **Source:** Author's estimate

Construction of Air Pollution Index

The purpose of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is to extract maximum information with minimum variables (latent variables or components). The goal of the PCA is to reveal how different variables change in relation to each other or how they are associated. This is achieved by transforming correlated original variables into a new set of uncorrelated (orthogonal) underlying variables (termed principal components), using the covariance matrix or its standardised form, which is the correlation matrix. In current literature, correlation has been often established but causation has not (Ricco et al., 2020). PCA is helpful in this regard because it allows diverse pollutants to be collapsed into a single API, which is further used through a GMM model in a multivariate causal framework with COVID-19 growth and control variables as well as climatic variables as determinants of air pollution.

The new components are a linear combination of the original ones and are sorted into descending order, according to the amount of variance (information) they account for in the original set of variables. Each new

component accounts for as much of the remaining total variance of the original data as possible. Cumulatively, all the new components account for 100 per cent of the variation. PCA involves calculating the Eigenvalues and their corresponding Eigenvectors of the covariance matrix or correlation matrix. Each Eigenvalue represents the total remaining variance accounted for the corresponding new variable.

With PCA methodology, it is possible to represent a principal component that contains all the information from an exact combination of the raw variables. Further, the use of rotated component scores is desirable if the objective is to get a clear interpretation of the simple summary of the information contained in the raw data. The scores are obtained by combining the raw variables with weights that are proportional to their component loadings. As more and more components are extracted, the measure of the explanatory power increases, but it is necessary to strike a balance between parsimony and explanatory power. PCA ensures that correlations among the original variables are large enough in a way that the first few new variables or principal components account for most of the variance. If this holds, no essential insight is lost by further analysis or decision making, and parsimony, as well as clarity in the structure of the relationships, are achieved.

The need for PCA arises because it helps with (i) achieving data reduction, (ii) making pollution variables uncorrelated with each other, and (iii) modelling with many dependent variables (pollutants) jointly. Unlike Ordinary Least Square (OLS), which minimises the sum of the squares of deviations, PCA maximises variance. Another feature of PCA is that it segregates inter-correlated variables into separate orthogonal factors or principal components. But most importantly, PCA can be used for developing a composite index that collapses a set of variables into a single variable to represent a complex phenomenon like air pollution.

Ordinarily, all components are not retained. Therefore, it is important to have a criterion for reducing the number of retained components. This is usually the Kaiser criterion, or Eigenvalue, which is a measure of the proportion of total variance explained by an observed variable. It should usually be equal to at least 1. The criterion is that any factor with an Eigenvalue ≥ 1 explains more variance than a single observed variable. This means that it explains more variation than it usually does on its own. Hence, it accounts for a part of the information of the omitted variables. Hence, the index formation technique is typically based on the following selection criteria:

- Components retained with Eigenvalue > 1 (or all components retained for completeness)
- The component score value should be at least 0.5
- No component score having a value less than 0

For this study, we have not used the Kaiser criterion (which may generate 1 or 2 retained components) with an Eigenvalue of more than one. Instead, to be more representative, we used the criterion of a fixed number of factors for the index. We feel that from a policy viewpoint, it would be more appropriate to take all four pollutants into consideration. Moreover, some important pollutants like CO₂ had been eliminated already. Hence, no further data reduction was desirable.

PCA as a method yields component scores that represent the relationship between retained principal components and variables. However, the initial component scores often do not lend themselves to a clear interpretation of the factors. Therefore, it becomes necessary to obtain the rotated component scores. These scores are more distinct in terms of orthogonalising the retained components and allowing for better interpretation. In other words, the initial scores are not distinctively eloquent or reflective of the dimensions. This is achieved by rotating the event space around the axes, for which there are various methods. We have used the varimax method for rotation. Further construction of the index is based on rotated component scores.

Index Formation and Causal Framework

The formation of a composite index for this study is based on Jha and Murthy (2006). The general method and the slight modification used are explained below:

- Once the number of retained principal components is determined and the rotated component scores are obtained, it is possible to generate the scientific weights required for collapsing all four variables into a composite index, which retains the full information of all four air pollutants and yet acts as a single composite variable. This enables the index to act as the dependent variable in a causal regression equation (GMM model).
- Jha and Murthy (2006) propose selecting one variable to represent each of the retained principal components.
- The variable that has the highest rotated component score is chosen to represent a particular component (say, the first component), provided that it has not already been chosen.
- If it has been chosen, the variable with the next largest loading is selected.
- The procedure starts with the largest principal component and proceeds to the smallest retained component (Lewis-Beck, 1994).

The index is constructed by applying the following formula:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n W_j X_j$$

Where,

X_j = retained variables

W_j = rotated component scores (weights) of retained components

n = number of retained components

j = index of the variable and its corresponding weight for variables 1, 2, 3...n

Construction of a composite index (API) leads to data reduction while retaining most of the omitted information—this is true of our index as well. The ensuing API should be so designed as to be interpreted in terms of a unidirectional code. This is true of our indices since all pollutants are bad for the environment and, hence, the higher the value of the index, the worse is its indication for the environment. The limitation of regression is that it is capable of representing only a one-to-many causal relationship—one dependant and many independent causal variables. It is not designed to represent a many-to-many causal framework. PCA, with the help of the Jha and Murthy (2006) method, is now (after tweaking) capable of developing a composite index (API) that can be used as a single dependant variable in a multivariate causal framework (regression), which is the proposed GMM model representing a one-to-many causal framework.

The four advantages of a similarly developed API are as follows:

1. A single composite (dependant) variable
2. Scientifically generated non-linear weights
3. All information retained
4. Unambiguous code for interpretation

By applying the Jha and Murthy (2006) procedure on the rotated component scores (Table 2), the following API for Delhi can be obtained:

$$\text{API} = 0.908 \times \text{NO}_2 + 0.955 \times \text{SO}_2 + 0.223 \times \text{CO} + 0.804 \times \text{PM}_{2.5}$$

APIs for the other cities have been constructed using the same methodology.

Testing for PCA

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity tests are the minimum standards for PCA and factor analysis. The values obtained for these tests indicate sampling adequacy and sphericity, which imply the appropriateness of factor analysis for the chosen data.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test: This test measures sampling adequacy for each variable in the model and the complete model. KMO returns values between 0 and 1. The statistic obtained is a measure of the proportion of variance among variables that might be a common variance.

The rule of thumb for interpreting the statistic is as follows:

- KMO values between 0.8 and 1 indicate that sampling is adequate.
- KMO values less than 0.6 indicate that sampling is inadequate and remedial action should be taken. Some authors put this value at 0.5.
- KMO values close to zero imply that there are large partial correlations compared to the sum of correlations. In other words, there are widespread correlations that are a large problem for factor analysis.

For our study, the values closer to 1 are better, and the value of 0.5 is the suggested minimum.

KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: This is the test for the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. In other words, if rejected, it would indicate that the structure of data permits the application of PCA. Taking this into consideration, this test provides the minimum standard to proceed for PCA. Small values ($P \leq 0.05$ level of significance) indicate that the null hypothesis stands rejected.

In our study, the value generated from the KMO test is greater than 0.5 in almost all cases except for Bengaluru, where it is 0.463 (close to 0.5), which suggests sampling adequacy for PCA and factor analysis. Similarly, for Bartlett's test of sphericity, small values (less than 0.05 of the significance level) indicate that factor analysis will be useful with the data for all cities. Hence, the results obtained in Table 1 indicate that both these test criteria are largely met.

Weights for Index Construction

The use of PCA has enabled us to generate scientific weights (Table 2) to collapse the four variables of CO, SO₂, NO₂ and PM 2.5 into a composite index called API. This index has been used in further analysis as the dependent variable in the main model that explains the relationship between COVID-19 growth and control along with climatic variables as determinants of air pollution. Due to the unavailability of consistent data on CO₂, which is a major air pollutant, we could not include the same in our analysis.

Table 2: Index Weights

Pollutant/City	SO ₂	No ₂	CO	PM2.5
Delhi	0.955	0.908	0.223	0.804
Mumbai	0.993	0.977	0.867	0.934
Bengaluru	0.982	0.99	0.972	0.984
Hyderabad	0.998	0.986	0.908	0.906
Chennai	0.995	0.965	0.991	0.955
Kolkata	0.964	0.88	0.872	0.889

Source: Author's own estimates

Analysing API

We gained insights into the relative position of each city, in terms of air pollution, through certain descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, CV, growth (ratio of minimum to maximum), and the mean to minimum mean ratio.

Table 3 presents comparative descriptive statistics for API for six major cities of India from 25 March 2020 to 19 October 202.

Table 3: Comparative Statistics for API

Criteria	Delhi	Mumbai	Kolkata	Chennai	Bengaluru	Hyderabad
Mean	104.72	64.56	64.23	73.35	79.73	76.38
Standard deviation	33.38	25.68	22.17	18.19	12.76	22.19
CV	31.87	39.78	34.52	24.80	16.00	29.05
Minimum	44.06	26.31	28.37	26.91	41.87	32.48
Maximum	192.39	167.39	143.88	109.10	129.84	155.94
Growth	22.90	15.72	19.72	24.66	32.25	20.83
Mean ratio	1.63	1.005	1	1.14	1.24	1.18

Note: Level of significance is 0.01 | **Source:** Authors' estimates

The mean ratio is a measure that serves as a guide for this study. Kolkata has the lowest mean index value. By taking Kolkata as the base, the calculation yields a ratio that signifies the proportion by which another city exceeds the minimum mean level of the best-performing city. Kolkata has the lowest mean value of API. Mumbai is just half a per cent above Kolkata, followed by Chennai, Hyderabad, Bengaluru and lastly Delhi, whose pollution level is 63 per cent more than the least, that is, Kolkata. On the other hand, Bengaluru has the lowest CV and Mumbai the highest. The ratio of the CV between Mumbai and Bengaluru is 2.5 times. This shows that pollution control in Mumbai is the poorest because extreme events are more frequent in Mumbai.

Table 4: Results for KMO and Bartlett's Test

City	Delhi	Mumbai	Kolkata	Chennai	Bengaluru	Hyderabad
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO)	0.599*	0.512*	0.606*	0.536*	0.463*	0.572*
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Chi-Square)	675.918*	211.046*	354.587*	79.73*	62.599*	184.559*

Note: * All statistically significant

AQI can lead to a misleading conclusion of air quality being poor or otherwise. In other words, with API, a low index value indicates that pollution is low, whereas, with AQI, a low index value might indicate that the pollution level is high. Hence, to facilitate accurate and true interpretation, AQI needs to be reported with a key or code, unlike for API, where the same would not be necessary.

Even some of the most celebrated indices, such as the Environmental Sustainability Index⁹ (ESI), fail to overcome the problem of establishing consistency in the code with the help of a set of data series, all of which are in absolute interval scale and yet so defined and chosen that they consistently point only in one direction resulting in a unique interpretation of the composite index that follows. There should be no ambiguity in interpreting the index on account of collapsing several variables together, which might not share the same code and direction.

Generalised Method of Moments

The GMM is practically the only estimation method that is justified in case of an endogeneity problem. In this issue, endogeneity may be an issue because the existing literature is replete with works that purport a two-way relationship between COVID-19 and pollution.

This is a statistical method that combines observed economic data with the information in population moment conditions to produce estimates of the unknown parameters of the economic model. GMM builds on the ideas of expected values and sample averages. Moment conditions are expected values that specify the model parameters in terms of the true moments. The sample moment conditions are the sample equivalents to the moment conditions. GMM finds the parameter values that are closest to satisfying the sample moment conditions.

Model in the General Form

Our model in the general form (Table 5) is as follows:

Air Pollution = F (Lockdown, Time, Daily Infections, Daily Recoveries, Humidity, Wind and Temperature)

Model in the Form of Estimated Equation

We have estimated the following equation from our general model:

$$IAPOL = e^{b_0} \times e^{b_1(COVDUM)} \times e^{b_2(TxCOVDUM)} \times e^{b_3(T)} \times (CASE)^{b_4} \times (RECOV)^{b_5} \times (HUM)^{b_6} \times (WIN)^{b_7} \times (TEMP)^{b_8}$$

9 ESI has been developed through a collaboration between the World Economic Forum, Geneva, Center for International Earth Science Information Network, Columbia University, and Yale Center for Environmental Law and Policy, New Haven.

Now if we take the natural logarithm of both sides, the above equation shall become as follows:

$$\ln(IAPOL) = b_0 + b_1(COVDUM) + b_2(TxCOVDUM) + b_3(T) + b_4 \ln(CASE) + b_5 \ln(RECOV) + b_6 \ln(HUM) + b_7 \ln(WIN) + b_8 \ln(TEMP)$$

Table 5: Legend for the Estimated Equation

Identifiers	Explanation
IAPOL	Index of Air Pollution
COVDUM	= 0 from 25 March 2020 to 31 May 2020 (period of complete lockdown) = 1 for domestic firms
T	Time starting from 25 March 2020 as "1" to 19 October 2020 with an increment of 1 for each day
CASE	Daily Infections
RECOV	Daily Recoveries
HUM	Humidity
WIN	Wind
TEMP	Temperature
b_0	Constant term
b_1	Percentage change in IAPOL due to un-lock, ceteris paribus
b_3	Percentage change in IAPOL due to increment in a time by one day, ceteris paribus
b_2 + b_3	Percentage change in IAPOL due to increment in a time by one day during the un-lock period, ceteris paribus
b_4	Percentage change in IAPOL due to a 1% increase in daily infections, ceteris paribus
b_5	Percentage change in IAPOL due to a 1% increase in daily recoveries, ceteris paribus
b_6	Percentage change in IAPOL due to a 1% increase in humidity, ceteris paribus
b_7	Percentage change in IAPOL due to a 1% increase in wind, ceteris paribus
b_8	Percentage change in IAPOL due to a 1% increase in wind, ceteris paribus

Generalised Methods of Moments Estimation for Regression Analysis

The OLS) method for regression analysis is based on certain assumptions, and if these assumptions are violated then our estimators lose consistency and efficiency. To overcome this problem, we used the GMM method instead of the OLS method for our regression analysis.

The advantages of the GMM method over the OLS method are as follows:

1. GMM method builds moments from the sample itself rather than depending upon assumptions.
2. While building moments from the sample itself, this method equates sample moments to population moments by making equations from samples and equating them with the population moments.
3. After building moments, this method tries to minimise the sum of these moments. However, each moment is not assigned equal weight but weight based on the inverse of sample variance. As a consequence, the moment that has the highest variance would get the lowest weight, and the moment that has the lowest variance would get the highest weight.
4. When moments are built in this manner, a study can get away with assumptions of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, thereby making this method more robust than the OLS method.

Regression Analysis for the six cities by using the GMM method in EViews 10 and our results are shown in Table 6.

Delhi: The results for Delhi during lockdown are ambiguous. At this time in Delhi, the API rose by 2 per cent. (This could be because dust storms from arid regions of Rajasthan are common in the summer months.) After lockdown, however, the API started to decline at the rate of 1 per cent per day. Daily cases of infections had a negative effect on the air pollution level. This is because people who were infected were isolated. This resulted in reduced levels of activities by these people and therefore less pollution. Recoveries show a positive sign but are not significant. Humidity, which was taken to be a proxy for precipitation, shows the expected negative sign. It bore a very large coefficient and was significant as well. Wind speed had the right sign (negative) but was not significant. Temperature had a negative sign and was significant. This is somewhat unexpected.

Mumbai: The city shows a negative impact of lockdown on air pollution and a 2 per cent rise after un-lockdown. Cases and recoveries show the expected sign and are significant as well. Humidity shows the expected negative sign. Wind speed had the right sign (negative) but was not significant. Temperature had a positive sign and was significant. Extreme temperature is expected to raise pollution.

Kolkata: In Kolkata, the result for lockdown is ambiguous. Both cases and recovery had a negative sign, even though recovery should have been positive. The climatic variables show the right signs.

Chennai: The impact of un-lock on air pollution levels in Chennai is similar to Delhi. The impact of cases and recoveries is converse. The coefficients of climatic variables like humidity and temperature are right but not significant. The co-efficient of wind speed is positive.

Bengaluru: All variables except humidity and wind speed are insignificant. They bear the right sign.

Hyderabad: All climatic variables are significant. Except for temperature, all variables show the right sign. Hyderabad too has its share of ambiguous results.

Table 6: GMM Estimates

	Delhi		Mumbai		Kolkata		Chennai		Bengaluru		Hyderabad	
	Parameter	P-Val										
Constant	12.661***	0.000	9.883***	0.000	5.658***	0.062	4.261***	0.010	6.616***	0.000	6.261***	0.000
COVDUM	0.697***	0.027	-1.367***	0.000	0.090	0.670	0.517**	0.089	-0.036	0.862	-0.048	0.833
TCOVDUM	-0.011**	0.059	0.020***	0.000	-0.003	0.383	-0.005	0.318	0.000	0.973	-0.004	0.226
T	0.020***	0.003	-0.012***	0.030	0.008**	0.082	0.009**	0.101	0.002	0.454	0.008**	0.090
ln (CASE)	-0.353***	0.001	-0.149*	0.119	-0.063	0.436	0.295***	0.005	-0.036	0.456	0.034	0.652
ln (RECOV)	0.021	0.768	0.076*	0.118	-0.109**	0.071	-0.317***	0.000	-0.021	0.601	-0.127**	0.069
ln (HUM)	-1.175***	0.000	-2.122***	0.000	-1.185**	0.088	-0.268	0.178	-0.284**	0.081	-0.329***	0.023
ln (WIN)	-0.026	0.532	-0.008	0.703	-0.237***	0.040	0.018	0.637	-0.101***	0.006	-0.126***	0.035
ln (TEMP)	-0.258***	0.002	1.410***	0.000	1.501***	0.000	0.089	0.802	-0.130	0.370	0.031	0.840
R2	0.415		0.661		0.441		0.553		0.317		0.458	
R	0.644		0.813		0.664		0.744		0.563		0.677	
J-Stat	27.652		19.512		25.356		20.816		17.633		20.283	
P-Value	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	

Notes: *** $0 < P\text{-Value} \leq 0.05$ | ** $0.05 < P\text{-Value} \leq 0.10$ | * $0.10 < P\text{-Value} \leq 0.15$ | **Source:** Authors' estimates

Conclusion

The ideal way to sum up this paper would be to revisit the research questions and try to answer them. This would be a vindication of the methodological and conceptual framework. It would also throw light on the vital questions that this paper has raised.

Hence, the five pertinent research questions are:

1. Do pollution patterns differ amongst metro cities?

There are wide differences among the six metro cities, with Delhi being the poorest in terms of air pollution by considering four individual air pollutants. However, it also throws light on the fact that the composition of air pollution is not the same in all six cities. The methodology of Jha and Murthy (2006) demonstrates that the scientific non-linear weights are different among the six metros. This raises the question of the efficacy of the established AQI.

2. When did COVID-19 peak in India?

By following the growth patterns of daily new cases and recoveries, it has been established at the all-India level that the turning point for the downturn is 18 September 2020.

3. Does the growth of COVID-19 impact air pollution in India?

Despite some inconsistencies, COVID-19 impacts air pollution in India, both directly and indirectly.

4. Does lockdown/un-lockdown impact air pollution in India?

While some results favour the hypothesis that lockdown reduces pollution, there is often ambiguity in this regard.

5. Do climatic variables impact air pollution in India?

The implications of climatic variables are by and large well-founded and bear the right sign.

This paper suggests a new approach towards measuring, modelling and analysing air pollution in the context of COVID-19 growth and control, climatic variables and un-lockdown.

References

- Bashir, M. F., Jiang, B., Komal, B., Bashir, M. A., Farooq, T. H., Iqbal, N., et al. (2020). Correlation between environmental pollution indicators and COVID-19 pandemic: a brief study in Californian context. *Environmental Research*, 187, 109652.
- Bontempi, E. (2020). First data analysis about possible COVID-19 virus airborne diffusion due to air particulate matter (PM): The case of Lombardy (Italy). *Environmental Research*, 186, 109639.
- Feng, H., Zou, B., Wang, J., & Gu, X. (2019). Dominant variables of global air pollution-climate interaction: Geographic insight. *Ecological Indicators*, 99, 251–260.
- Holtmann, M., Jones, M., Shah, A., & Holtmann, G. (2020). Low ambient temperatures are associated with more rapid spread of COVID-19 in the early phase of the endemic. *Environmental Research*, 186, 109625.
- Jha, R., & Murthy, K. V. B. (2006). Environmental degradation index: A survey of composite indices measuring country performance—2006 Update, 35–36. A UNDP/ODS Working Paper, by Romina Bandura with Carlos Martin del Campo, Office of Development Studies, United Nations Development Programme, New York.
- Lewis-Beck, M.S. (1994). *Factor Analysis and Related Techniques*, Sage Publications.
- Murthy, K. V. B., & Gambhir, S. (2020). Conceptualization and Measurement of Air Pollution Index in the South Asian Context (Conference Presentation). 5th Biennial International Conference, Sri Guru Gobind Singh College of Commerce, University of Delhi, New Delhi, 6–7 March.
- Murthy, K. V. B., & Kumar, L. (2020). Measuring climate change in India: A retrospective on the past century (Conference Presentation). IIF International Research Conference and Award Summit, 27–29 September.
- Otmani, A., Benchrif, A., Tahri, M., Bounakhla, M., El Bouch, M., & Krombi, M. H. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 lockdown on PM10, SO₂ and NO₂ concentrations in Salé City (Morocco). *Science of the Total Environment*, 735, 139541.
- Ramanathan, V., & Feng, Y. (2009). Air pollution, greenhouse gases and climate change: Global and regional perspectives. *Atmospheric Environment*, 43(1), 37–50.
- Riccò, M., Ranzieri, S., Balzarini, F., Bragazzi, N.L., & Corradi, M. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 infection and air pollutants: Correlation or causation? *Science of the Total Environment*, 734, 139489.

- Singh, V., Singh, S., Biswal, A., Kesarkar, A. P., Mor, S., & Ravindra, K. (2020). Diurnal and temporal changes in air pollution during COVID-19 strict lockdown over different regions of India. *Environmental Pollution*, 266, 115368.
- Zhu, Y., Xie, J., Huang, F., & Cao, L. (2020). Association between short-term exposure to air pollution and COVID-19 infection: Evidence from China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 727, 138704.

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